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Research Article

Synergistic Detection and Quantification of Gliclazide and Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate from Tablet Dosage Form by Derivative Spectroscopy Method.

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ABSTRACT

The present study outlines the development of a highly specific and reproducible first-order derivative spectroscopic method for the quantitative estimation of Gliclazide, a Potassium channel blocker, and Dapagliflozin, an SGLT-2 inhibitor, from their synthetic combination. Both compounds belong to the antidiabetic drug class. The analytical procedure was established using a Shimadzu double-beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer integrated with UV Probe 2.71 software, employing methanol as the solvent. Gliclazide was quantified at 228 nm, the zero-crossing point of Dapagliflozin, while Dapagliflozin was measured at 222 nm, the zero-crossing point of Gliclazide. The method demonstrated linearity in the concentration ranges of 15–75 µg/mL for Gliclazide and 5–25 µg/mL for Dapagliflozin. Accuracy studies yielded recovery rates of 99.78–100.30% for Gliclazide and 99.47–99.98% for Dapagliflozin. The method was validated in accordance with ICH Q2(R1) guidelines and proved suitable for the simultaneous quantitative analysis of the synthetic mixture.

INTRODUCTION

Gliclazide (GLIC) is an antidiabetic agent belonging to the sulfonylurea class, which acts by stimulating insulin secretion from pancreatic β -cells. It achieves this by blocking ATP-sensitive potassium channels, leading to cell depolarization and subsequent insulin release. Gliclazide is primarily used in the management of type 2

diabetes mellitus, either as monotherapy or in combination with other oral hypoglycemic agents. Dapagliflozin (DAPA), on the other hand, is a sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitor. It is used alongside diet and exercise to enhance glycemic control in adults with type 2 diabetes. SGLT2 is a key transporter responsible for renal glucose reabsorption; its inhibition

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promotes glucosuria and reduces blood glucose levels in diabetic patients.

According to the clinical trial study of an ongoing international real-world investigation (ADD2DIA) assessing the effectiveness of adding an SGLT2 inhibitor, such as Dapagliflozin, to a Gliclazide MR (modified-release) regimen in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). This combination leverages complementary mechanisms: Gliclazide stimulates insulin secretion, while Dapagliflozin promotes urinary glucose excretion. The study found that this combination improved glycemic control without a significant increase in hypoglycemia risk and also contributed to weight reduction.

Figure 1 Structure of Gliclazide

Figure 2 Structure of Dapagliflozin

The above drug combination is marketed as a tablet dosage form with Gliclazide 30 mg and Dapagliflozin 10 mg. Several analytical methods have been reported for the individual or combined analysis of GLICLA and DAPA with other drugs, literature reveals no validated method specifically for their simultaneous estimation from a synthetic mixture or formulation. UV spectrophotometric techniques offer greater operational simplicity compared to chromatographic methods.

Moreover, derivative spectroscopy enhances method specificity by allowing quantification at the Zero Cross Over Point (ZCP). Therefore, derivative spectroscopic analysis was chosen as the preferred method for the simultaneous estimation of Gliclazide and Dapagliflozin from their combined marketed formulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material

DAPA (99.98% pure) and GLICLA (99.96% pure) were obtained as gift sample for research purpose from, Cadila Healthcare Ltd., Sanand. Methyl alcohol (AR grade) was purchase from Finar. Sample processing was performed using Shimadzu UV1900i double beam spectrophotometer having path length of 1 cm matched pair of quartz cells. Obtain spectra of GLICLA and DAPA were derivatized 1st order using UV probe 2.72 as software at delta λ of 10 nm. equipment.

Preparation of Master Stock Solution:

For the method development purpose, 30 mg of GLICLA and 10 mg of DAPA were precisely weighed and then transferred to 100 mL volumetric flasks. The level was raised with methanol to produce a solution containing 300 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ GLICLA and DAPA, respectively.

Selection of Analytical Wavelength:

The working standards of GLICLA (15-75 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and DAPA (5-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were prepared in 10 ml volumetric flask using methyl alcohol as a solvent. They were scanned in the UV range of 200 – 400 nm and D^0 spectra is recorded by UV spectrophotometer. All the D^0 spectra of GLICLA and DAPA were transformed into D^1 spectra with the help of UV probe 2.42 software. For

confirmation of D¹ spectra of GLICLA and DAPA, D⁰ and D¹ spectra of the same were overlapped.

Preparation of solutions for analytical method validation

Preparation of solution for linearity and range

To check linearity of method, GLICLA was prepared in the concentration range of 15-75 µg/mL and DAPA was prepared in the range of 5-25 µg/mL from master stock solution in 10 ml volumetric flask. When D1 Absorbance was plotted against concentration, non-linearity

was observed above 100 µg/mL for GLICLA and above 35 µg/mL for DAPA, so final range for validation was selected at mixture containing 15-75 µg/mL for GLICLA and 5- 25 µg/mL for DAPA. All prepared solutions were scanned between 200-400 nm and all spectra were derivatized to 1st order. D¹ absorbance were obtained at selected wavelength and mean D¹ absorbance was plotted against concentration (To get mean D¹ absorbance, procedure was repeated for five times)

Intermediate precision (Repeatability)

To adjudge the repeatability of analytical method, solution of linearity studies were analysed for five time with same conditions. Mean D¹ absorbance was recorded at all concentrations for GLICLA and DAPA and were observed for relative standard deviation.

Method precision

Method precision was determined by performing intraday and interday precision. Mixture that represents overall range (15+5, 45+15 and 75+25 µg/mL) were analyzed on same day at different time interval for intraday precision. Mixture that represents overall range (15+5, 45+15 and 75+25 µg/mL) were analyzed on different days for interday precision.

Accuracy study

Accuracy of analytical method was adjudged by spiking of blank with standard solution. Standard solution was spiked at 50, 100 and 150% of target concentration (30+10 µg/mL) (Table 1). Each spiked concentration was analyzed for three times and mean % recovery was observed at each spiked level.

Table 1 Preparation of solutions for accuracy studies

Concentration of stock solution (Sample)	300 µg/mL GLICLA + 100 µg/mL DAPA			
Volume of Standard taken in ml from stock solution of standard	1 mL	1 mL	1 mL	1 mL
Concentration of stock solution (Standard)	300 µg/mL GLICLA + 100 µg/mL DAPA			
Volume of Standard taken in ml from stock solution of standard	-	0.5 mL	1 mL	1.5 mL
Diluent (Up to 10 ml)	Methanol	Methanol	Methanol	Methanol
Concentration corresponding to standard solution taken (GLICLA+DAPA)	-	15+5 µg/mL	30+10 µg/mL	45+15 µg/mL
Identification	Unspiked	50 % Spiked	100 % Spiked	150 % Spiked

Assay

Average weight of 10 tablet was calculated, 325.75 mg powder (equivalent to 30 mg of GLICLA + 10 mg of DAPA) transferred to 10 ml

volumetric flask. Volume make up was done with methanol (GLICLA+DAPA = 300+100 µg/mL) Sonicated for 10 minutes and filter through 0.45 micron Whatman filter paper) Withdraw 1.0 mL of master stock solution in 10 ml volumetric flask; make up the volume with methanol, which contain 30 µg/mL of GLICLA and 10 µg/mL of DAPA. This mixture was scanned between 200-400 nm and was derivatized to 1st order. D¹ absorbance was measured at selected wavelengths and were transformed to concentration with help of linear regression equation. This mixture was analyzed for three times and mean % assay was drawn.

Result and Discussion

Selection of analytical wavelength

Four different ZCP at 212 nm, 228 nm, 260 nm and 287 nm were observed in overlain D¹ spectra of GLICLA (Figure 3). Five different ZCP at 217 nm, 222 nm, 255 nm, 275 nm and 300 nm different ZCP at 256 nm, 275 nm and 305 nm were observed in overlain D¹ spectra of DAPA (Figure 4). For determination of analytical wavelength D¹ spectra of GLICLA and DAPA were overlapped (Figure 5). But there is very less difference between absorbance values of DAPA at 260 nm and hence difficulty in quantifying the same. Discussed problem can be eliminated at 222 nm, where the D¹ absorbance values of DAPA are linear with significant difference (Figure 6). In similar way at ZCP of DAPA, linearity was observed only at 228 nm for GLICLA (Figure 7). So 222 nm and 228 nm were selected as analytical wavelength for quantitative determination of DAPA and GLICLA respectively.

Figure 3 Zero cross over point of GLICLA

Figure 4 Zero cross over point of DAPA

Figure 5 Overlain D1 spectra of GLICLA and DAPA

Figure 6 Determination of DAPA (25 µg/mL) at ZCP of GLICLA

Figure 7 Overlain of D1 spectra of GLICLA [15-75µg/mL] and DAPA [5-25 µg/mL]

Analytical method validation

All validation parameters were studied as per ICH guidelines.^{25,26}

Linearity and range

When D^0 spectra of GLICLA was taken between 15 – 75 µg/mL, non-linearity was observed over 100 µg/mL. So, linearity for GLICLA was observed between 15 – 75 µg/mL. for method development purpose range was selected between 15 - 75 µg/mL (based on beer — lambert's law).

In similar way D⁰ spectra of DAPA was taken between 5 - 25 µg/mL, but non-linearity was observed over 35 µg/mL. So, linearity for DAPA was observed between 5 - 25 µg/mL. and for method development purpose range was selected between 5 - 25 µg/mL (based on beer — lambert’s law). So final range for validation was selected at mixture containing 15 – 75 µg/mL for GLICLA

and 5 - 25 µg/mL for DAPA. When calibration curve was plotted for given concentration range (Figures 7 and 8), value of linear regression coefficient was found to be 0.9971 for GLICLA and 0.9961 for DAPA. Regression equation was found to be $y = 0.0007x - 0.0016$ for GLICLA and $y = -0.0008x + 0.0005$ for DAPA. Linearity data for both drugs is shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2 Linearity data of GLICLA

Sr no.	Concentration [µg/mL]	Mean ± SD	RSD
1	15	0.00782±0.00013	1.67
2	30	0.0187±0.0002	1.46
3	45	0.02942±0.00033	1.14
4	60	0.0408±0.0004	1.05
5	75	0.05202±0.00042	0.81

$y = 0.0007x - 0.0016$, Correlation Coefficient $R^2 = 0.9971$

Figure 8 Calibration curve of GLICLA (15-75 µg/mL)

Table 3 Linearity data of DAPA

Sr no	Concentration [µg/mL]	Mean area ± SD	RSD
1	5	0.00344 ± 5.47723	1.59
2	10	0.00744±0.00011	1.53
3	15	0.01162±0.00016	1.41
4	20	0.0155±0.00018	1.21
5	25	0.02068±0.00023	1.15

$y = -0.0008x + 0.0005$ Correlation Coefficient $R^2 = 0.9961$

Figure 9 Calibration curve of DAPA (5-25 µg/mL)

Repeatability

When all mixtures were analyzed at all concentration, calculated relative standard deviation at each level was found to be less than 2

so that method was found to be repeatable over the range of 15 - 75 µg/mL for GLICLA and 5 - 25 µg/mL for DAPA. Repeatability data are shown in table 4 and 5 for GLICLA and DAPA respectively.

Table 4 Repeatability data of GLICLA

Concentration (µg/mL)	15	30	45	60	75
abs 1	0.0079	0.0188	0.0294	0.0408	0.0519
abs 2	0.0077	0.0187	0.0298	0.0402	0.0525
abs 3	0.008	0.0191	0.0292	0.0406	0.0524
abs 4	0.0078	0.0184	0.0297	0.0411	0.0518
abs 5	0.0077	0.0185	0.029	0.0413	0.0515
Mean	0.00782	0.0187	0.02942	0.0408	0.05202
SD	0.00013	0.0002	0.00033	0.0004	0.00042
RSD	1.67	1.46	1.14	1.05	0.81

n= 5 determinations

Table 5 Repeatability data of DAPA

Concentration (µg/mL)	5	10	15	20	25
abs 1	0.0034	0.0075	0.0118	0.0157	0.0205
abs 2	0.0035	0.0073	0.0117	0.0156	0.0207
abs 3	0.0035	0.0074	0.0114	0.0155	0.021
abs 4	0.0034	0.0076	0.0115	0.0152	0.0204
abs 5	0.0034	0.0074	0.0117	0.0155	0.0208
mean	0.00344	0.00744	0.01162	0.0155	0.02068
SD	5.47723	0.00011	0.00016	0.00018	0.00023
RSD	1.59	1.53	1.41	1.21	1.15

n= 5 determinations

Method precision

For determining inter day and intraday precision, % RSD was monitored at selected concentration

level which was found to be less than 2 so method was found to be precise for estimation of GLICLA and DAPA. Data for intermediate precision are

given in Tables 6 and 7 for GLICLA and DAPA, respectively.

Table 6 Intraday and Inter-data of GLICLA

Concentration (µg/mL)	Intraday Mean ± SD	RSD	Inter-day Mean ± SD	RSD
15	0.00790 ± 0.00013	1.68	0.00788 ± 0.00012	1.60
45	0.02928 ± 0.00033	1.15	0.0295 ± 0.00030	1.22
75	0.05170 ± 0.00040	0.86	0.05136 ± 0.00047	0.92

n = 3 determinations

Table 7 Intraday and Inter-data of DAPA

Concentration (µg/mL)	Intraday Mean± SD	RSD	Inter-day Mean± SD	RSD
5	-0.00334 ± 0.00513	1.53	-0.00335 ± 0.00453	1.73
15	-0.01200 ± 0.00017	1.44	-0.01190 ± 0.00017	1.46
25	-0.02076 ± 0.00023	1.11	-0.02053 ± 0.00025	1.23

n= 3 determinations

Accuracy study

which was found within 98 to 102, so method was found to be accurate (Table 8 & 9).

Spiked placebo with standard solution at 50, 100 and 150% level was analyzed for % recovery

Table 8 Accuracy data of GLICLA

Level of spiking	Amount of drug added (µg/mL)	Amount of drug recovered(µg/mL)	% Recovery
50 %	15	14.97 ± 0.31	99.78 ± 2.04
100 %	30	29.83 ± 0.35	99.44 ± 1.17
150 %	45	45.13 ± 0.83	100.30 ± 1.85

n= 3 determinations for each set

Table 9 Accuracy data of DAPA

Level of spiking	Amount of drug added (µg/mL)	Amount of drug recovered(µg/mL)	% Recovery
50 %	5	4.97 ± 0.11	99.47 ± 2.20
100 %	10	9.96 ± 0.12	99.63 ± 1.18
150 %	15	15.00 ± 0.27	99.98 ± 1.78

n= 3 determinations for each set

Assay

found to be 97.89 ± 3.56 for GLICLA and for 99.23 ± 1.57 DAPA (Table 10)

When prepared synthetic mixture was analyzed by developed and validated method, % assay was

Table 10 Determination of GLICLA and DAPA from mixture

Drug	Amount taken [µg/mL]	Amount found [µg/mL]	% Assay
GLICLA	30	29.37 ± 1.07	97.89 ± 3.56
DAPA	10	9.92 ± 0.16	99.23 ± 1.57

CONCLUSION

The 1st order derivative spectroscopic method was developed and validated as per ICH Q2 R1 guidelines and was successfully applied for determination of GLICLA and DAPA from its synthetic mixture. Present method was found to be economical in terms of cost and time. Commonly used excipient didn't interfere in estimation of GLICLA and DAPA so method was found to be specific. Method was also found to be repeatable and precise.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

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REFERENCES

1. Indian Pharmacopoeia. Government of India: Ministry of Health and family welfare Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, Ghaziabad, Edition 8, 2018: 3, 3799-3800.
2. Gupta AK: Quality Standard of Indian Medicinal Plants. Indian Council of Medicinal Research, New Delhi, 2003: 8, 138-148.
3. Martin D: The Complete Drug Reference. Pharmaceutical Press, London, Edition 35, 2007: 1326.
4. The Merck Index: An Encyclopedia of Chemicals, Drugs, and Biologicals. Merck Research Laboratory, U.S.A., Edition 14, 2006: 1687.
5. Indian Pharmacopoeia. Government of India: Ministry of Health and family welfare Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, Ghaziabad, Edition 8, 2018: 3, 3771-3772.
6. Ulanowska M, Olas B. Biological properties and prospects for the application of eugenol—A review. *Int J Mol Sci* 2021;22:3671.
7. Nikhat P, Amber J. Eugenol—A review of a versatile molecule with remarkable pharmacological properties. *J Adv Sci Res* 2021;12(8):8-12.
8. Muhammad FN, Mahnoor K, Muhammad R, Jinyin C, Yali Y, Chunpeng CW. Pharmacological properties and health benefits of eugenol: A comprehensive review. *Oxid Med Cell Longev* 2021;2021:1-7.
9. Suchitra P, Rajashree H. A new stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for determination of curcumin: An application to nanoparticulate formulation. *Int J Pharm Pharmacol* 2016;8(12):149-55.
10. Haroon KS, Kai BL, Gabriel OK, Kok KP. Stability indicating HPLC–UV method for detection of curcumin in *Curcuma longa* extract and emulsion formulation. *Food Chem* 2015;170:321-6.
11. Sultana S, Vandana J. Development and validation of a RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of curcumin, piperine and camphor in an ayurvedic formulation. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2018;10:115-21.
12. Ankita K, Srinivas B, Rajashree H. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of

- curcumin and piperine. *Int J Appl Pharm* 2018;10(5):43-8.
13. Neha D, Munira M, Upasana S, Tabassum K, Atul S. Analytical method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of curcumin and cyclosporine by RP-HPLC. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2019;11:26-33.
 14. Rubiya K, Sachin KS, Bhupinder K, Monica G, Sheetu W, Saurabh G, Prateek P, Deep K, Kamal D, Sharath LM, Babu UV, Manish S, Hardik S, Vijay K. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous determination of curcumin and quercetin in extracts, marketed formulations, and self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system. *Regen Med Genomics Open* 2021;1(1):43-52.
 15. Reolon JB, Maicon B, Sandra EH, Eduardo AB, Marcelo DM, Leticia MC. Development and validation of high-performance liquid chromatography method for simultaneous determination of acyclovir and curcumin in polymeric microparticles. *J Appl Pharm Sci* 2018;8(1):136-41.
 16. Ankalgi DA, Nitin KC, Pooja K, Mahendra AS. Method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of methotrexate and curcumin in bulk drug by using RP-HPLC. *J Drug Deliv Ther* 2019;9.
 17. Duygu E, Mustafa C, Derya D, Sacide A. RP-HPLC method development for determination of curcumin in commercial turmeric capsules. *Hacet Univ J Fac Pharm* 2024;44(1):1-8.
 18. Sagar S, Sasikumar M, Sunita S, Priyanka P. Validated RP-HPLC method to estimate eugenol from commercial formulations like Caturjata Churna, Lavangadi Vati, Jatiphaladi Churna, Sitopaladi Churna and clove oil. *J Pharm Res* 2013;6(1):53-60.
 19. Zeynep A, Gülcemal Y, Ece MY, Hassan YA. Determination of eugenol in plants and pharmaceutical form by HPLC with amperometric detection at graphene-modified carbon paste electrode. *Graphene Technol* 2018;3:1-9.
 20. Kannissery P, Ura KI, Yoonuskunju TK, Sayeed A, Shahid HA, Javed A. Development and validation of RP-HPLC-PDA method for the quantification of eugenol in developed nanoemulsion gel and nanoparticles. *J Anal Sci Technol* 2013;4:1-6.
 21. Rana IS, Aarti SR, Ram CR. Evaluation of antifungal activity in essential oil of the *Syzygium aromaticum* (L.) by extraction, purification and analysis of its main component eugenol. *Braz J Microbiol* 2011;42(4):1269-77.
 22. Balkrishna A, Sharma P, Joshi M, Srivastava J, Varshney A. Development and validation of a rapid high-performance thin-layer chromatographic method for quantification of gallic acid, cinnamic acid, piperine, eugenol, and glycyrrhizin in Divya-Swasari-Vati, an ayurvedic medicine for respiratory ailments. *J Sep Sci* 2021;44(16):3146-57

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